

APPROACHES AFFECTING QUALITY OF LIFE OF THE ELDERLY IN PHRAYA PRASIT COMMUNITY, DUSIT DISTRICT, BANGKOK

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Abstract

The objective of the current study is to examine the role of status in community and household status of elderly people in quality of life (QOL) in Phraya Prasit Community, Dusit District, and Bangkok, Thailand. A survey is carried out by considering the cross-sectional research design. While data collection through questionnaire, 130 questionnaires were received by the current study and used in data analysis. Data analysis is carried out by using Smart PLS 3. Total seven hypotheses were tested in which five hypotheses were based on direct effect and two hypotheses were based on mediation effect of life satisfaction. It is found that; status in community and household status has positive effect on elderly people's QOL. Improvement in status in community and household status of elderly people can increase the QOL among them. Findings shows that; status in community and household status can increase the life satisfaction which further causes to increase QOL.

Keywords. Quality of life, status in community, household status, life satisfaction.

1. Introduction

Several organizations are working on the rights of elder people in the community (Marcos-Pardo et al., 2019). Although the elder people must have a significant level of respect as well as rights must be provided to them. However, there are several issues related to the elderly people's rights. The elder people community is living in all countries and related to various organizations as well as community and domestic level. Based on the seniority as well as better experience of life and various other matters the community must be treated as respectful. First of all, the rights of this community must be fulfilled, however, there are several issues are found based on the elderly people in Thailand.

Especially, the elderly people living in in Phraya Prasit Community, Dusit District, Bangkok, Thailand required a significant level of respect as well as dignity. Therefore, the quality of life (QOL) of elderly people is one of the problems in the community (Bullo et al., 2018; de Oliveira, Souza, Rodrigues, Fett, & Piva, 2019). The people living in various communities are not enjoying the QOL due to several issues. The issues at community level as well as household level does not allow the elderly people to spend a quality life. Thus, the provision of QOL to the elder people is most important, however, it is a challenging task. Number of previous studies address the QOL through different aspects (Aruta, Callueng, Antazo, & Ballada, 2022; Duong et al., 2022). Previous studies also addressed the QOL of elderly people (Gutiérrez-Vega, Villar, Armando, Carrillo-Saucedo, & Montañez-Alvarado, 2018; Lu, Wu, Mao, & Liang, 2020). However, the QOL of elderly people in relation to the status in the community is not considered. Additionally, the role of household status in QOL of elderly people is also not addressed by the previous studies. The important role of status in community and household status of elderly people in relation to the life satisfaction as well as QOL is needed to address.

Status in community and household status has major importance to achieve the QOL among the elderly communities. Therefore, the objective of the current study is to examine the role of status in community and household status of elderly people in QOL. Along with the status in community and household status the current study also considered life satisfaction in relation to the QOL which also has major importance. Therefore, along with the direct effect, this study also considered the mediating role of life satisfaction to promote QOL of elderly people.

2. Hypotheses Development

Bangkok, Thailand's capital, is a large city known for ornate shrines and vibrant street life. Phraya Prasit Community, Dusit District is the part of Bangkok, Thailand which is considered in this study to examine the elderly people QOL. To consider the QOL, this study addressed the role of status in community and household status of elderly people in Bangkok. Furthermore, the life satisfaction is also considered in this study. The relationship between status in community, household status, life satisfaction and QOL is considered in this study which is shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1. The relationship between status in community, household status, life satisfaction and quality of life

Status of the elderly people in the community has major importance in their life. As better status in the community received by the elder people lead to the satisfaction level. The status in the community has direct relationship with QOL. Because status is one of the important measures of QOL for any person (Abdel-Rahman, 2019). The better status given by the community to specific person always causes to increase the level of quality in life. Similarly, among the elder people the status is most important to achieve quality in life. In this way, the satisfaction is playing most important role (Martyr et al., 2018). The role of satisfaction in QOL is mandatory (Mei et al., 2021). The fluctuation in life satisfaction always causes to increase or decrease the quality level. Therefore, the study purposed that life satisfaction has major role in QOL (Wu et al., 2018). However, life satisfaction is influenced by the several factors. Along with the other factors, status in community is one of the factors which can effect life satisfaction. Therefore, the effect on life satisfaction due to the status in community can lead

to the QOL. Thus, life satisfaction is playing the mediating role between status in community and QOL. Therefore, the current study proposed following hypotheses;

Hypothesis 1. Life satisfaction has positive relationship with QOL.

Hypothesis 2. Status in community has positive relationship with QOL.

Hypothesis 3. Status in community has positive relationship with life satisfaction.

Hypothesis 4. Life satisfaction mediates the relationship between status in community and QOL.

Moreover, household status of elderly people also has major importance in their life. Any change in the household status may effect on the QOL. Household status can be described as the level of respect as well as participation in various matters of household. The elderly people at household level must be receive all the rights including the holding of resources as well as participation in various matters. Based on the more experience in the life, the elderly people can take various important decisions. The participation of elderly people in various matters of household can lead to the better decision making. The elder people living in any society or any household must have decision making power and their participation must be ensured in various matters. Therefore, the better level of participation in various household matters lead to the higher household status. However, lower participation of elder family members in various matters lead to the lower status. The lower status of family members leads to the low QOL. At domestic level, the increase in life satisfaction can be achieved with the help of better status. As life satisfaction has positive effect on QOL (Karimi, Rezaee, Shakiba, & Navidian, 2019; Şimşek, Koç, Özsoy, & Karakuş, 2020), therefore, the household status must be promoted to increase the level of life satisfaction among elderly people. Therefore, household status causes to increase life satisfaction which has positive effect on QOL. Thus, life satisfaction is playing the role of mediating variable between household status and QOL. Hence, following hypotheses are proposed;

Hypothesis 5. Household status has positive relationship with QOL.

Hypothesis 6. Household status has positive relationship with life satisfaction.

Hypothesis 7. Life satisfaction mediates the relationship between household status and QOL.

3. Methodology

The current study considered the relationship between status in community, household status, QOL and life satisfaction. The nature of this relationship is based on primary data, therefore, the study considered quantitative research approach. By considering quantitative research approach, this study employed cross-sectional research design. This design is considered because nature of the study is not supported the longitudinal research design. This research design is a most suitable to collect data for the current study. For this purpose, this study designed a survey questionnaire by adopting various measures of status in community, household status, life satisfaction and QOL. Status in community is measured by considering the level of participation by the elderly people in various matters of community. Household

status is also measured in similar way and decision-making power of elderly people at household level is considered. In this process, the decision-making ability of the people is considered. Furthermore, life satisfaction is considered by asking various questions related to the resources available to spend the quality life. Finally, this study measured QOL by asking various questions related to the satisfaction in the life. After the development of survey questionnaire, 300 questionnaires were distributed among the elderly people. The respondents of the current study were the elderly people living in Phraya Prasit Community, Dusit District, Bangkok, Thailand. This study distributed these questionnaires among the people above 50-year age. Finally, 130 questionnaires were received by the current study and used in data analysis. The questionnaires were distributed with the help of cluster sampling which is most suitable data collection technique to cover more population.

4. Findings

Data screening is important element among the research studies because data screening is important to remove various errors in the data (Ahmad et al., 2018). The probability of errors is quite significant while data collection as well as data entry in the Excel sheet. Thus, the removal of various error such as missing value, outlier in the data and normality of data is most important because it may effect on the results. The data statistics of the current study are shown in Table 1. Therefore, the study carried out data screening in which missing value, outlier and normality of data is considered. It is found that QOL has seven missing values and household status has three missing values. Additionally, it is found that QOL has four outliers and community status has five outliers. All the missing values as well as outlier are fixed with the help of recommended methods.

Table 1. Data Statistics

	No.	Missing	Mean	Median	Min	Max	SD	Kurtosis	Skewness
SC1	1	0	4.098	4	1	5	0.908	1.312	-0.841
SC2	2	0	3.649	4	1	5	1.106	-0.374	-1.56
SC3	3	0	2.902	4	1	5	0.974	-1.682	-0.461
SC4	4	0	3.996	4	1	5	0.964	0.508	-1.921
SC5	5	0	4.093	4	1	5	0.846	1.324	-0.977
SC6	6	0	3.813	4	1	5	1.042	-0.22	-0.688
HS1	7	0	4.064	4	1	5	0.971	-1.42	-1.702
HS2	8	0	3.569	4	1	5	1.142	-0.68	-0.451
HS3	9	0	3.613	4	1	5	1.214	-1.647	-1.545
HS4	10	0	3.711	4	1	5	0.904	-0.453	-0.565
HS5	11	0	3.662	4	1	5	1.084	-0.03	-0.645
HS6	12	0	3.916	4	1	5	0.898	1.25	-1.982
LS1	13	0	3.88	4	1	5	1.011	-0.409	-0.589
LS2	14	0	4.071	4	1	5	0.945	0.172	-0.811
LS3	15	0	3.876	4	1	5	0.963	-0.077	-0.651
LS4	16	0	3.924	4	1	5	0.97	0.738	-0.936
LS5	17	0	3.52	4	1	5	1.088	-0.481	-0.417

QoL1	18	0	3.676	4	1	5	1.074	-0.317	-0.582
QoL2	19	0	3.56	4	1	5	1.281	-0.848	-0.472
QoL3	20	0	3.578	4	1	5	1.27	-1.011	-0.385
QoL4	21	0	3.742	4	1	5	1.176	-0.354	-0.693
QoL5	22	0	3.742	4	1	5	1.172	-0.813	-0.537
QoL6	23	0	3.764	4	1	5	1.223	-0.798	-0.583
QoL7	24	0	3.231	3	1	5	1.215	-0.939	-0.167

The current study employed partial least square (PLS) as a statistical tool to analyse the data (Hameed, Nisar, & Wu, 2021). It is based on two major steps and the first step of this statistical tool is highlighted in Figure 2 with the name of measurement model. In measurement model the current study considered to check the reliability as well as validity of the data. Reliability is considered by considering the factor loading, alpha and composite reliability (CR). First of all, the results of factor loading are given in Table 2 which shows that all the items have factor loading above 0.5 which is least threshold level in the present study. Figure 2 shows that status in community is measured by six items and household status is measured by six items and all the scale items have factor loading above 0.5. Furthermore, QOL is measured by using seven scale item and life satisfaction is measured by using five items and none of the item has factor loading below 0.5.

Figure 2. Measurement Model

Table 2. Factor Loadings

	Household Status	Life Satisfaction	QOL	Status in Community
HS1	0.523			
HS2	0.88			
HS3	0.894			
HS4	0.894			
HS5	0.882			
HS6	0.566			
LS1		0.65		
LS2		0.761		
LS3		0.849		
LS4		0.705		
LS5		0.646		
QoL1			0.737	
QoL2			0.887	
QoL3			0.903	
QoL4			0.911	
QoL5			0.899	
QoL6			0.882	
QoL7			0.769	
SC1				0.709
SC2				0.612
SC3				0.702
SC4				0.678
SC5				0.653
SC6				0.653

After the assessment of factor loading, this study considered composite liability which is shown in Table 3 and the value of composite reliability (CR) must be higher than 0.7 (Basco et al., 2021; Hair et al., 2020; Joseph F Hair Jr et al., 2021; Purwanto & Sudargini, 2021). Along with composite reliability the study also inspected average variance extracted (AVE) which must be above 0.5 as shown in Table 3. The values of composite reliability and AVE is above 0.7 and 0.5 respectively which confirmed the convergent validity.

Finally in first step of data analysis, this study also addressed discriminant validity which is also important to address and recommended by several previous studies. In this process the study considered cross-loading to check the discriminant validity which is given in Table 4. All the values in Table 4 achieved the recommended criteria which fulfill the requirement of discriminant validity.

Table 3. Reliability and Convergent Validity

	Alpha	rho_A	CR	AVE
Household Status	0.867	0.893	0.905	0.624
Life Satisfaction	0.777	0.784	0.846	0.527
QOL	0.939	0.94	0.951	0.736
Status in Community	0.755	0.764	0.829	0.547

Table 4. Cross-Loadings

	Household Status	Life Satisfaction	QOL	Status in Community
HS1	0.623	0.467	0.386	0.592
HS2	0.88	0.547	0.661	0.621
HS3	0.894	0.5	0.672	0.629
HS4	0.894	0.528	0.631	0.586
HS5	0.882	0.456	0.592	0.61
HS6	0.566	0.432	0.372	0.472
LS1	0.353	0.65	0.336	0.415
LS2	0.366	0.761	0.329	0.443
LS3	0.434	0.849	0.471	0.596
LS4	0.375	0.705	0.356	0.573
LS5	0.611	0.846	0.703	0.574
QoL1	0.659	0.631	0.737	0.604
QoL2	0.586	0.619	0.887	0.577
QoL3	0.607	0.582	0.903	0.581
QoL4	0.613	0.55	0.911	0.588
QoL5	0.657	0.523	0.899	0.597
QoL6	0.573	0.463	0.882	0.539
QoL7	0.585	0.487	0.769	0.517
SC1	0.479	0.481	0.463	0.709
SC2	0.405	0.33	0.432	0.612
SC3	0.779	0.541	0.704	0.802
SC4	0.387	0.521	0.323	0.678
SC5	0.361	0.595	0.325	0.653
SC6	0.454	0.458	0.347	0.653

In second step of data analysis in Figure 3 shows the structural model (Joe F Hair Jr et al., 2020; Joseph F Hair Jr et al., 2021). The structural model examined the effect of status in community and household status on life satisfaction and quality of lie. In this process, this study also considered the effect of life satisfaction on QOL. The mediating effect of life satisfaction is considered in this type of data analysis. All the results of hypotheses are shown in Table 5. In this process the study shows that status in community has significant effect on life satisfaction. Status in community also has significant effect on QOL. It is found that household status also has significant relationship with life satisfaction. The relationship

between household status and QOL is also significant. It is found that life satisfaction has significant and positive effect on QOL

Figure 3. Structural Model

Table 5. Direct Effect Results

	Beta	(M)	SD	T Statistics	P Values
Household Status -> Life Satisfaction	0.16	0.16	0.064	2.483	0.007
Household Status -> QOL	0.446	0.447	0.079	5.671	0
Life Satisfaction -> QOL	0.265	0.258	0.063	4.237	0
Status in Community -> Life Satisfaction	0.62	0.621	0.059	10.472	0
Status in Community -> QOL	0.144	0.152	0.084	1.713	0.044

After the assessment of direct effect the study also considered the indirect effect. The first mediation effect of life satisfaction is considered between status in community and QOL. The second mediation effect of life satisfaction is considered between household status and QOL. Results indicated in Table 6 shows that life satisfaction as a mediating variable between status in community and QOL is significant. The second mediation effect of life satisfaction between household status and QOL is also significant. The acceptance of these hypotheses shows that life satisfaction transfers the positive effect of status in community and household status on QOL. Finally, this study considered r-square value which is 0.589. This value indicated that all

the variables such as status in community, household status and life satisfaction is expected to bring 58.9% change in QOL which is moderate.

Table 6. Indirect Effect Results

	Beta	(M)	SD	T Statistics	P Values
Status in Community -> Life Satisfaction -> QOL	0.164	0.16	0.042	3.941	0
Household Status -> Life Satisfaction -> QOL	0.042	0.041	0.019	2.286	0.011

5. Discussion

The current study examined the QOL of elderly people in Thailand. Several studies have carried out the quality-of-life investigation of elderly people in Thailand but the role of elderly people status in community as well as in household status is not considered by previous studies. To fill this literature gap, the current study considered the effect of status in community and household status of elderly people on QOL. Furthermore, the current study also highlighted the mediating role of life satisfaction.

The current study proposed seven hypotheses in which five hypotheses are based on direct affect and two hypotheses are based on indirect effect. Hypothesis 1 indicated the relationship between status in community and QOL. The results shows that status in community has direct relationship with QOL. It indicates that better status in the community of elderly people has positive effect on QOL. However lower status in community by the elderly people may have negative effect on the QOL. With the increase in age the elder people must have a significant level of status in the community. Furthermore, the effect of status in community is also considered in relation to the life satisfaction in hypothesis 2. This hypothesis is also significant and shows that there is a direct effect of community status on life satisfaction. Results indicated that the satisfaction in life by elderly people can be promoted with the help of better status in the community. Therefore, the status of elderly people has major importance in the community as it causes to decrease or increase in the QOL with the help of life satisfaction. Furthermore, hypothesis 3 shows the effect of household status on QOL of elderly people. Along with the other relationships this relationship is also significant which shows the direct effect of household status on QOL. Similar with the status in community, the status in household also has direct effect on QOL of elderly people. It shows that higher status at household level can increase the QOL. Therefore, the study highlighted that the respect of the elder people in the society as well as at household level causes to increase the QOL. Furthermore, the involvement of elderly people in various decision-making processes at community level and at household level also has the ability to enhance QOL. Hypothesis 4 indicated the effect of household status on life satisfaction. These two variables also have significant and positive effect. It shows that with the increase in household status, life satisfaction can increase significantly. Finally, while considering the direct effect of variables, this study considered the relationship between life satisfaction and QOL in hypothesis 5. It is found that there is a direct effect of life satisfaction

on quality-of-life. Thus, betterment in job satisfaction among the elderly people is most important to promote QOL in Thailand. Finally, it is concluded that there are two major approaches to promote QOL. These approaches include the better status of elderly people in the community and household level increases the level of life satisfaction among them which further increases the quality-of-life. It is observed from the findings of the study that life satisfaction transfers the positive effect of status in community and household status on QOL.

6. Implications of the Study

Theoretically the current study has major implications due to the unique relationship tested in this study. Majorly the current study tested the effect of community status and household status of elderly people on QOL. Number of studies addressed the QOL of elder people as well as QOL, however, the previous studies have not considered community status of elderly people. Nevertheless, studies also not considered the effect of household status on QOL. It is also observed that the current study filled the literature gap by considering the relationship between life satisfaction and status in community. Additionally, this study contributed by considering the effect of household status of elderly people on life satisfaction. All these relationships have not considered by the previous studies; therefore, this study has major theoretical implications. Practically, this study is also important for the organisations who serve elderly people. In Thailand, the organisations who serve elderly people must consider the status of the elder people in the community and at household level. As the improvement in status at household as well as community level causes to increase the QOL among elderly people in Thailand.

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